

PEDAGOGICAL VALUES. EDUCATION AS A UNIVERSAL VALUE

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Annotation: In this article, the concept of pedagogical value, its content, scope of application. Factors determining the essence of value, the role and importance of values in pedagogical professional activity are discussed.

Key words: value, activity, essence, attitude, fact, education, upbringing, innovation, technology, system, development

Pedagogical values are the norms that regulate pedagogical activity and act as a system of cognitive activity that serves as a mediator and connecting link between the existing social worldview in the field of education and teacher's activity. They, like other values, are historically formed and strengthened by the science of education as a form of social consciousness in the form of certain images and ideas. Educational activities are carried out in the process of mastering pedagogical values, their subjectivization occurs during this period. The degree of subjectivization of these pedagogical values serves as an indicator of the teacher's personal and professional development.

Pedagogical values also change with the change of social conditions of life, the development of society and individual needs. Thus, in the history of pedagogy, there are changes associated with the transformation of scholastic theories of learning into explanatory-illustrative, and later into problematic theory. The strengthening of democratic tendencies leads to the development of non-traditional forms and methods of teaching. The subjective perception and determination of pedagogical values is determined by the wealth of the teacher's personality, the direction of his professional activity.

Classification of pedagogical values. Pedagogical values differ in the degree of their existence. On this basis, social, group and personal pedagogical values can be distinguished.

Social pedagogical values reflect the nature and content of the values that operate in different social systems, manifesting themselves in the public mind. It is a set of ideas, perceptions, norms, rules, and traditions that regulate the activities of the society in the field of education.

A group of pedagogical values can be presented in the form of ideas, concepts, norms that regulate and control pedagogical activity within the framework of certain rules. educational institutions... Such a set of values has a holistic nature, relative stability and reproducibility.

Personal pedagogical values act as socio-psychological formations that reflect the teacher's goals, motives, ideals, attitudes and other features of the worldview, which in their totality form the system of his value orientations. Axiological (from the Greek Ah1a - value) "I" as a system of value orientations includes not only cognitive, but also emotional-volitional components that play the role of its internal reference point. He assimilates both socio-

pedagogical and professional-group values, which serve as the basis for the individual-personal system of pedagogical values. This system includes:

Values related to the confirmation of a person's role in the social and professional environment (the social importance of a teacher's work, the prestige of pedagogical activity, recognition of the profession by the closest personal environment, etc.);

Meeting the need for communication and expanding its scope (communication with children, colleagues, children's experience of love and affection, exchange of spiritual values, etc.);

Directing creative individuality to self-development (opportunities to develop professional and creative skills, get acquainted with world culture, engage in a favorite subject, continuous self-improvement, etc.);

Allowing for self-realization (creative character is the work of a teacher, the romance and charm of the teaching profession, the opportunity to help socially disadvantaged children, etc.);

Creating an opportunity to meet pragmatic needs (the possibility of obtaining a guaranteed need for public service, salary and vacation time, work experience, etc.).

Values-goals act as a dominant axiological function in other pedagogical value systems, because goals reflect the main meaning of the teacher's activity.

The goals of pedagogical activity are determined by specific motives corresponding to the needs that are implemented in it. This explains their leading position in the hierarchy of needs, which includes the needs for self-development, self-realization, self-improvement, and the development of others. In the teacher's mind, the concepts of "child personality" and "I am a professional" are interrelated.

Looking for ways to realize the goals of pedagogical activity, the teacher chooses his professional strategy, the content of which is the development of himself and others. Consequently, the values-goals reflect the state educational policy and the level of development of the science of pedagogy, become subjectivized and become important factors of pedagogical activity and influence. Instrumental values are called mean-values. They are formed as a result of assimilation of theory, methodology and formation of the basis of pedagogical technologies of vocational education teacher.

Values - tools - these are three interconnected subsystems: 1) correct pedagogical actions aimed at solving problems of professional, educational and personal development (teaching and educational technologies); 2) communicative actions to enable the implementation of personal and professionally oriented tasks (communication technologies); 3) actions that reflect the subjective essence of the teacher are integrative in nature, because they combine all three subsystems of actions into a single axiological function.

Values-tools are divided into the following groups: values-relationships, values-attributes and values-knowledge.

Values-relationships provide the teacher with appropriate and adequate construction of the pedagogical process and his interactions with his subjects. The attitude towards professional activity does not remain unchanged and changes depending on the success of the teacher's actions, the level of satisfaction of his professional and personal needs. Value attitude to pedagogical activity, which determines the way of mutual relations between the teacher and students, is distinguished by the direction of humanity. In value relationships, the attitude of the teacher to himself as a professional and his attitude as a person are equally

important. Here it is legitimate to refer to the existence and dialectics of "I-real", "I-retrospective", "I-ideal", "I-reflexive", "I-professional". The dynamics of these images determine the level of personal and professional development of the teacher.

In the hierarchy of pedagogical values, values are qualities, because they reflect the teacher's personal and professional characteristics. These include various and interrelated individual, personal, status-role and professional-activity qualities. These qualities arise from the level of development of a number of abilities: predictive, communicative, creative (creative), empathetic (from the Greek *empathia* - empathy, the ability to enter into the emotional experiences of a person with the help of emotions. other people, sympathize with them), intellectual, reflective and interactive.

Values-relationships and value-characteristics cannot ensure the necessary level of pedagogical activity if the subsystem of value-knowledge is not formed and mastered. It includes not only psychological, pedagogical and subject knowledge, but also their level of awareness, the ability to select and evaluate them based on the conceptual personality model of pedagogical activity.

Knowledge values are a certain orderly and organized system of knowledge and skills presented in the form of pedagogical theories of personality development and socialization, laws and principles of the construction and operation of the educational process, etc. Mastery by the teacher. fundamental psychological-pedagogical knowledge creates conditions for creativity, allows navigating professional information, solving pedagogical problems at their own level. use of modern theory and technology, effective creative methods of pedagogical thinking.

Thus, the named groups of pedagogical values form each other and form an axiological model with a syncretic (Greek - *synkreti-mo* - connection, unification) character. It is manifested in the fact that values-goals determine values-means, and values-relationships depend on values-goals and values-characteristics, etc., that is, they all function as a whole. This model can serve as a criterion for accepting or rejecting developed or created pedagogical values. It determines the tonality of culture, implies a selective approach to the values existing in the history of this or that nation, as well as to the newly created works of human culture. The axiological wealth of the teacher determines the effectiveness and appropriateness of choosing and increasing new values, their transfer to the motives of behavior and pedagogical actions.

This article examines the values of pedagogical activity, their role in educational standards and professional activity standards. The essence of pedagogical values is illuminated from the point of view of modern studies... A classification is presented that allows to fully systematize the pedagogical values of a modern teacher.

The study of pedagogical values was carried out by the following scientists: A.A. Korostylev, V.A. Slastenin, G.I. Chizhakova, J. Hazard, E.N. Shiyanov, I.F. Isaev, N. Yu. Guzeva, S.G. Vershlovsky.

Value - material-objective characteristics of events, psychological characteristics of a person, positive and negative values of events that represent public life for an individual or society.

V.A. Slastenin and G.I. Chizhakova derives from the fact that pedagogical values are models of orientation of consciousness and personality behavior, distinguishing dominant, normative, motivating and accompanying values. It should be noted that this approach is

largely reflected in the "Concept of Spiritual and Moral Development and Education of a Russian Citizen" (authors AY Danilyuk, AM Kondakov, VA Tishkov).

I.F. Isaev suggests the following classification of teacher's professional values:

- values-goals - values that reveal the meaning and meaning of the goals of the teacher's professional and pedagogical activity;
- values - means - values that reveal the meaning of methods and means of professional and pedagogical activity;
- values-relationships - values that reveal the meaning and meaning of relations as the main mechanism of integrated pedagogical activity;
- values-knowledge - values that reveal the content and meaning of psychological-pedagogical knowledge during the implementation of pedagogical activities;
- values-characteristics - values that reveal the meaning and meaning of the qualities of the teacher's personality: various interrelated individual, personal, communicative, professional qualities of the teacher's personality professional-pedagogical activity manifests itself as special abilities: creative ability, the ability to plan one's activities and foresee their consequences.

A significant step in the development of the problem of values of pedagogical activity E.N. Shiyonov. The values of pedagogical activity means the means that allow to satisfy the material, spiritual and social needs of the teacher, the goals that serve as guidelines for his social and professional activity. As a basis for classifying personal needs and their compatibility with the teaching profession, he identified the following types of values: values related to the confirmation of a person in society, the closest social environment; values related to meeting the need for communication; values related to self-improvement; values related to self-expression and utilitarian-pragmatic values.

Korostyleva, the personal potential of the teacher can be considered as a system of interrelated and interconnected components: freedom of choice and action within the framework of pedagogical consistency; professional responsibility and semantic potential as a combination of personal and professional values and meanings. Here, the main focus is on the teacher as the carrier of certain semantic constructions and the subject of their development. N.Yu. Guzev, considered the problem of formation of professional directions of the future teacher in the conditions of teacher training college, defines three groups of pedagogical values:

1) values related to the conditions of professional activity:

- "freedom" in the pedagogical process;
- constant communication with people;
- detailed work process;
- humanitarian nature of the profession;
- continuous self-improvement;
- knowledge of your subject;
- respect and gratitude of people;
- creative nature of work;

2) values related to the teacher's personal motivational sphere:

- availability of professional growth prospects;
- continuation of family traditions;
- compatibility of the profession with inclinations and interests;

- desire to be in the center of people's attention;
- 3) educational activity of values reflecting management aspects:
 - the ability to influence the behavior of others and lead them;
 - affection is the relationship between a teacher and a student;
 - the ability to convey your skills and knowledge.

S.G. Vershlovsky and J. Hazard studied the value orientations of Russian and American teachers and identified the following groups of pedagogical values:

- 1) values that reveal the teacher's professional status;
- 2) values that indicate the level of a person's involvement in the teaching profession;
- 3) values reflecting the goals of pedagogical activity.

As you can see, for the authors, the basis for emphasizing pedagogical values was job satisfaction and the possibility of self-realization in professional activity, but this, in our opinion, does not reflect the entire diversity of pedagogical values.

Thus, we can say that the values of pedagogical activity mean the values of the teacher himself, the values of the pedagogical team, as well as the generally accepted values of the person who serves as a guide in professional activity.

In the scheme we created, we identified and included the following values of pedagogical activity: we connected the belief to the personal values of the teacher, because each person has his own ideals. The teacher should teach children about faith, positive attitude of people to the world around them. We also, like any other person, attributed health to the teacher's personal values. First of all, the teacher must monitor his own health, indirectly teach children to do the same, for example: hygiene and self-care, giving up bad habits, etc.

Work is a personal value, which should be included not only as a material benefit, but also as a moral and moral attitude of people to the profession and an awareness of the social importance of the teacher's activity.

Since the teacher should value and respect each child and take the task of forming his personality, the child should act as a value for the teacher.

Freedom is the absence of obstacles and compliance with wishes, the teacher's free choice of the curriculum and methods of teaching it.

Some people who have a pedagogical education and do not realize themselves in another field of activity go to work by profession not because they like it, but by force, and then the value of their pedagogical activity is monetary and material. there will be wealth.

We associate justice as the values of the team of teachers with the group values, because teachers should have an objective attitude to situations that arise in the team, solve problems fairly, because a teacher who teaches children justice is a role model for himself. should be

Professional work can be valuable for teachers. Creative nature of work, reputation, love and connection to work with children. A teacher is professionally prepared if he has pedagogical knowledge, skills, and important professional qualities related to cognitive and motivational areas.

Scientific education can be a value because it allows the teacher to develop himself, self-awareness, is a "trigger" for the formation of the teacher's scientific and cognitive interest. cognitive activity child.

Culture acts as a set of material and spiritual values achieved in the process of mastering the world, with the help of which society integrates, ensures the functioning and interdependence of its institutions.

The teacher's social values are universal values (truth, virtue, beauty), which are important for all mankind and are aimed at developing spirituality, freedom, and equality among all members of society.

Thus, we can conclude that the teacher is the main person in the educational process and the value orientations of children depend on him. Currently, it is very important for the teacher to correctly define the pedagogical value system, because they play an important role as the highest level of regulation of human behavior in the formation of the teacher's personality, expresses the interests and behavior of his specific attitude and motivation in the field of pedagogical activity

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